

NOTE ON A CONGRUENCE INVOLVING PRODUCTS OF BINOMIAL COEFFICIENTS

Ping Xu

Department of Mathematics, Nanjing University, Nanjing 210093, People's Republic of China
pingxu_nju@yahoo.com.cn

Hao Pan

Department of Mathematics, Shanghai Jiaotong University, Shanghai 200240, People's Republic of China
haopan79@yahoo.com.cn

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Abstract

We prove that for integers $n, m \geq 2$ with $(n, 2m) = 1$,

$$(-1)^{\frac{\phi(n)(m-1)}{2}} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{d|n} \binom{d-1}{[dk/m]}^{\mu(n/d)} \equiv m(m^{\phi(n)} - 1) + 1 \pmod{n^2},$$

where $\phi(n)$ is the Euler totient function. This generalizes a result of Granville.

The Main Result

As early as 1895, Morley [4] proved a beautiful congruence as follows:

$$(-1)^{(p-1)/2} \binom{p-1}{(p-1)/2} \equiv 4^{p-1} \pmod{p^3}, \tag{1}$$

where $p \geq 5$ is a prime. In [2], Granville extended the result of Morley and showed that

$$(-1)^{\frac{(p-1)(m-1)}{2}} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \binom{p-1}{[pk/m]} \equiv m^p - m + 1 \pmod{p^2} \tag{2}$$

for any prime $p \geq 3$ and $m \geq 2$, where $[x]$ denotes the greatest integer not exceeding x . For further extensions of Granville's result, the reader may refer to [6]. A q -analogue of (2) has been established in [5].

With the help of a generalization of Lehmer's congruence, Cai [1] proved that

$$(-1)^{\phi(n)/2} \prod_{d|n} \binom{d-1}{(d-1)/2}^{\mu(n/d)} \equiv 4^{\phi(n)} \begin{cases} \pmod{n^3} & \text{if } 3 \nmid n, \\ \pmod{n^3/3} & \text{if } 3 \mid n, \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

for any odd positive integer n , where $\phi(n)$ is the Euler totient function. Inspired by Cai's result, in this note we generalize Granville's congruence (2) to arbitrary integers $n, m \geq 2$ with $(n, 2m) = 1$.

Theorem 1. *For any integers $n, m \geq 2$ with $(n, 2m) = 1$, we have*

$$(-1)^{\frac{\phi(n)(m-1)}{2}} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{d|n} \binom{d-1}{\lfloor dk/m \rfloor}^{\mu(n/d)} \equiv m(m^{\phi(n)} - 1) + 1 \pmod{n^2}.$$

First, we require a lemma on the quotients of Euler.

Lemma 2. *Let n be a positive integer and a be an integer with $(a, n) = 1$. Then*

$$\frac{a^{\phi(n)} - 1}{n} \equiv \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{aj} \left\lfloor \frac{aj}{n} \right\rfloor \pmod{n}. \tag{4}$$

Proof. Let $1 \leq r_j \leq n$ be the least non-negative residue of aj modulo n for every $j \in \mathbb{Z}$. It is easy to see the set $\{r_j : 1 \leq j \leq n, (j, n) = 1\}$ coincides with $\{j : 1 \leq j \leq n, (j, n) = 1\}$, since if $j_1 \not\equiv j_2 \pmod{n}$ then $r_{j_1} \neq r_{j_2}$. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} a^{\phi(n)} &= \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \frac{aj}{j} = \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \frac{\lfloor aj/n \rfloor n + r_j}{j} = \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \frac{r_j}{j} \left(1 + \frac{\lfloor aj/n \rfloor n}{r_j} \right) \\ &= \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \left(1 + \frac{\lfloor aj/n \rfloor n}{r_j} \right) \equiv 1 + n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \frac{1}{r_j} \left\lfloor \frac{aj}{n} \right\rfloor \pmod{n^2} \\ &\equiv 1 + n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^n \frac{1}{aj} \left\lfloor \frac{aj}{n} \right\rfloor \pmod{n^2}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark. When n is a prime, the result of Lemma 2 was first discovered by Lerch [3].

Proof of Theorem 1. Let $P_d = \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \binom{d-1}{\lfloor dk/m \rfloor}$ and $Q_d = \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,d)=1}}^{\lfloor dk/m \rfloor} \left(\frac{d}{j} - 1 \right)$. Then $P_n =$

$$\prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{j=1}^{\lfloor nk/m \rfloor} \left(\frac{n}{j} - 1 \right) = \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{d|n} \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (n,j)=d}}^{\lfloor nk/m \rfloor} \left(\frac{n}{j} - 1 \right) = \prod_{d|n} Q_{n/d} = \prod_{d|n} Q_d.$$

By using the inverse

formula for the Möbius function, $Q_n = \prod_{d|n} P_d^{\mu(n/d)} = \prod_{d|n} \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \binom{d-1}{\lfloor dk/m \rfloor}^{\mu(n/d)}$. On the other

hand, define $N = \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} |\{j : 1 \leq j \leq \lfloor nk/m \rfloor, (j, n) = 1\}|$ and apply Lemma 2 to get

$$\begin{aligned} (-1)^N Q_n &= \prod_{k=1}^{m-1} \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{\lfloor nk/m \rfloor} \left(1 - \frac{n}{j}\right) \equiv 1 - n \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{\lfloor nk/m \rfloor} \frac{1}{j} \pmod{n^2} \\ &= 1 - n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{j} \sum_{k=\lfloor mj/n \rfloor + 1}^{m-1} 1 = 1 - n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{m-1 - \lfloor mj/n \rfloor}{j} \\ &= 1 - n(m-1) \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{j} + nm \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{\lfloor mj/n \rfloor}{mj} \\ &\equiv m(m^{\phi(n)} - 1) + 1 \pmod{n^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the last congruence follows from

$$\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{j} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \left(\frac{1}{j} + \frac{1}{n-j}\right) = \frac{n}{2} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \frac{1}{j(n-j)} \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{\lfloor nk/m \rfloor} 1 = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \sum_{k=\lfloor mj/n \rfloor + 1}^{m-1} 1 = \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \left(m-1 - \left\lfloor \frac{mj}{n} \right\rfloor\right) \\ &= (m-1)\phi(n) - \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \left(\frac{mj}{n} - \left\{ \frac{mj}{n} \right\}\right) \\ &= (m-1)\phi(n) - \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ (j,n)=1}}^{n-1} \left(\frac{mj}{n} - \frac{j}{n}\right) = \frac{\phi(n)(m-1)}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\{x\} = x - \lfloor x \rfloor$. □

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